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Deliverable 8

Best Practice Guide on the traceable measurement and characterisation of SMPs/NPs in food and environmental matrices

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Deliverable Cover Sheet

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Executive Summary

An international interlaboratory comparison (ILC) was organised in 2024, with statistic support provided by the Plastic Trace project, to validate ISO 16094-2: Water quality — Analysis of microplastics in water – Part 2: Vibrational spectroscopy methods for waters with low content of suspended solids including drinking water. Eleven laboratories from eight countries analysed three reference materials using μ (FT)IR and μ Raman spectroscopy. Results were evaluated statistically according to ISO 5725-2 to assess repeatability, reproducibility, and recovery.

The study showed that the ISO 16094-2 methodology delivers satisfactory performance under repeatability conditions, with robust recovery for particles $\geq 50 \mu\text{m}$. However, reproducibility across laboratories remained limited, with significant variability for mixed-polymer and high-concentration samples. Measurements could be extended down to $20 \mu\text{m}$, but with increased uncertainty, reflecting analytical challenges at smaller size ranges.

Overall, the ILC provides the first systematic validation of ISO 16094-2. The results confirm its robustness for clean water analysis while highlighting the need for greater harmonisation of laboratory practices, improved operator training, and the development of reliable reference materials below $50 \mu\text{m}$ to strengthen reproducibility and comparability worldwide.

1. GENERAL INTRODUCTION

Interlaboratory comparison (ILC) studies on microplastics (MPs) have so far focused mainly on environmental matrices such as water, sediments, and biota. These exercises have consistently revealed large discrepancies between laboratories in detection limits, size ranges, and reported particle concentrations, largely attributable to differences in sample preparation and the performance of analytical techniques such as (FT)IR, Raman spectroscopy, Py-GC-MS, and TED-GC-MS. The outcomes highlight the urgent need for harmonised protocols and the development of well-characterised reference materials, since the lack of suitable test materials remains a major obstacle to comparability and proficiency testing. To address this gap, stakeholders have emphasised the importance of establishing a central repository of diverse, quality-controlled MP test materials—covering different polymer types, fragment shapes, and pristine versus aged forms—to enable reliable and reproducible interlaboratory comparisons (Belz et al., 2024).

A recent ILC organised within the VAMAS (Versailles Project on Advanced Materials and Standards) framework confirmed these challenges. Results demonstrated substantial variability across laboratories, particularly in particle counts, size distributions, and polymer identification, with acceptable consistency achieved only for larger particles (>100 μm). Variability arose mainly from differences in analytical approaches ((FT)IR, Raman, Py-GC-MS, TED-GC-MS) and sample preparation practices, with quantification of smaller particles (<20 μm) remaining especially difficult (Ciornii et al., 2025). These findings reinforce the central role of ILCs in standardising methodologies for MP characterisation, as they help identify best practices, highlight limitations, and ultimately ensure the reproducibility and reliability of results across laboratories.

Within this context, the Plastic Trace project aimed to use ILCs—both among consortium partners and with external laboratories—to assess state-of-the-art measurement capabilities for MPs in food and environmental matrices, and to evaluate the suitability of project-developed materials as candidate reference materials. To this end, LNE, INRIM, Nestlé Waters, BAM, and NIVA jointly designed an ILC strategy targeting selected SMP/NP neat materials. Among these initiatives, specific support was provided to an ILC organised for the validation of ISO 16094-2, Water quality — Analysis of microplastics in water – Part 2: Vibrational spectroscopy methods for waters with low content of suspended solids including drinking water. LNE contributed by performing the statistical data treatment based on ISO 5725-2 (repeatability and reproducibility). PET tablets produced within the project were selected as test materials by the ILC Organising Committee and distributed to participants worldwide.

The present work reports the results of this ILC, conducted in 2024, which served as a cornerstone for the validation of ISO 16094-2—the first international technical standard dedicated to the analysis of MPs in clean waters by vibrational spectroscopy. Results were presented to the ILC participants, to the ISO Annual Meeting of the ISO TC147 / SC2 / JWG1 Microplastics in October 2024, and were included in the Annex G of the standard. A peer-reviewed publication detailing the results of this ILC study is currently in preparation and under submission.

Published in September 2025 (<https://www.iso.org/standard/84460.html>), the ISO 16094-2 standard establishes core principles for the investigation of MPs in drinking water and in waters with low suspended solids, marking a key achievement of the Plastic Trace project.

2. AIM OF THE ISO 16094-2 INTERLABORATORY COMPARISON

The objective of this study was to evaluate the performance of ISO 16094-2 methodology for the detection, identification and quantification of microplastics in water through a structured interlaboratory comparison. Specifically, the work aimed to assess the method's repeatability, reproducibility, and recovery across different particle sizes, polymer types, and particle number concentration levels, using μ (FT)IR and μ Raman spectroscopy. By analysing results from internationally recognized laboratories and applying ISO 5725-2

statistical treatment, the study seeks to confirm the robustness of the standard, identify sources of variability, and provide recommendations to improve future applications, particularly for smaller particle size classes.

3. STUDY DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

3.1. Selection of participating laboratories and timeline

A validation interlaboratory trial was organized in 2023 and 2024. Due to the limited amount of materials available for the ILC, not all the registered participants could participate to exercise. Twelve expert laboratories were selected through a technical questionnaire. Selection of laboratories was based on demonstrated competence according to ISO 33405(ISO 33405:2024, 2024): method validation parameters including general practices employed in order to minimise the samples contamination by microplastics, previous participation in other ILC for the same measurands, use of test/reference materials, and third-party assessment of conformity with ISO/IEC 17025 or other relevant standards for the determination of MP number. The capability to analyse the same sample (same filter) by both μ (FT)IR and μ Raman techniques was also considered. Finally, 11 laboratories from 8 different worldwide countries, Austria, France, Germany, Italy, Japan, Singapore, South Korea, and USA, participated to the exercise and submitted the results. Participants belonged from different types of institutions as government agencies, research institutes, industries, commercial labs, universities and national metrology institutes. Samples were sent to the participants earlier 2024 and measurements were conducted between February and July 2024. Collected results were statistically treated in the summer and presented to the ISO Annual Meeting in Seoul (ISO TC147 / SC2 / JWG1 Microplastics) in October 2024. The variety of instruments (μ (FT)IR and μ Raman) and other analytical conditions used conformed to the quality parameters as specified in the ISO methodology.

3.2. Tested materials

For the evaluation of analytical approaches for detection, identification and quantification of microplastics in water by vibrational spectroscopy, three sets of test materials (ISO-A, ISO-B, ISO-C) were analysed in the validation trial, representing different types of polymers, different sizes and different total particle number concentrations of MPs (Table 1).

Table1. Materials tested in the comparison exercise. The assigned value, X , is the total particle number characterised by the supplier with an expanded associated uncertainty ($k=2$).

Label	Material type	Conditioning	Assigned value	Supplier
ISO-A	Low numbers of microplastics, different types of polymer, size down to 50 μ m	Mix of tablets called to reconstitute two samples + blank tablet sample	196 \pm 22	NIVA
ISO-B	High numbers of microplastics, one type of polymer, size down to 30 μ m	Glass vials containing salt carrier microplastic + surfactant + deionized water to reconstitute one sample	302-484	JRC
ISO-C	Low numbers of microplastics, one type of polymer, size down to 20 μ m	Glass vials containing one blank tablet and one test tablet as to reconstitute two samples	28 \pm 20	BAM

The current state of the art in the production of reference materials for microplastics is, to date, limited to achieving homogeneous material down to a particle size of 20 – 50 μm . Sample ISO-A was produced by the Norwegian Institute for Water Research (Norwegian: Norsk institutt for vannforskning, NIVA) and delivered as a mix of tablets that were reconstituted in water by the participants to obtain two samples – Mix A and Mix B. Mix A contained 3 types of polymers: PE, PP and PVC, whereas Mix B contained three different types of polymers: PET, PP and PC. Sample ISO-B, produced by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission, was reconstituted by the participants by transferring the salt cake containing microplastics with the aid of the surfactant solution into the deionized water (Jacob et al., 2024; JRC Technical Report, 2021). The salt cake and the surfactant solution components were provided in glass vials, while the deionised water was provided in a glass bottle. No assigned value was established for ISO-B at the time of the ILC; however, considering homogeneity as well as short- and long-term stability, a range of 300 to 480 particles (Feret min) was expected. Sample ISO-C was provided by the German Federal Institute for Materials Research and Testing (Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und –prüfung, BAM) in the form of a tablet that was used to reconstitute the sample in water (Altmann et al., 2025, submitted to *Journal of Hazardous Materials Advances*). Furthermore, blank water to reconstitute the samples and two blank tablets provided with ISO-A and ISO-C sets had to be analysed by the participants. The blank control samples were used to evaluate the eventual contaminations of the samples and the laboratory environment.

3.3. Measurement Techniques

The participating laboratories were asked to apply the ISO16094-2 norm for Raman and (FT)IR spectroscopy as they are doing in routine measurement. Materials and methods are covered by the method detailed in the standard (ISO 16094-2:2025, 2025).

4. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS AND DATA TREATMENT

Measurement results were statistically evaluated for repeatability and reproducibility in accordance with ISO 5725-2:2020 (ISO 5725-2:2020, 2020). ISO 5725 uses two terms, “trueness” and “precision”, to describe the accuracy of a measurement method (ISO 5725-1:2023, 2023): **trueness** refers to the closeness of agreement between the arithmetic mean of a large number of test results and the true or accepted reference value. **Precision** refers to the variability between replicate measurements of identical items under identical circumstances, arising from unavoidable random errors in any measurement procedure. It encompasses two extremes: **repeatability**, where all influential factors remain constant and contribute minimally to variability, and **reproducibility**, where some or all influential factors vary and increase variability. Precision is typically expressed as standard deviations. According to ISO 5725-2, these parameters are estimated through repeatability and reproducibility standard deviations, determined from the interlaboratory study in which each laboratory performs multiple independent measurements of the same sample under repeatability conditions (ISO 5725-2:2020, 2020).

Statistical data processing was performed using LNE’s in-house InterLab-R Shiny software, which is designed to analyse interlaboratory comparison data following the ISO 5725-2 guidelines for determining repeatability and reproducibility. The basic method described in ISO 5725-2 applies to standardized procedures that are regularly used in multiple laboratories, which is the case for this ILC. It also requires a balanced, uniform-level experiment, with the same number of test results in each laboratory and the same levels of test samples. This condition was not always met due to the limited availability of material and participants and two analytical methods (Raman and (FT)IR). Consequently, particular effort was invested in the data treatment to maximise the number of repetitions and thereby enhance statistical robustness.

The following parameters were calculated: the overall mean of results (\bar{x}), the estimate of the repeatability variance (s_r), the estimate of the reproducibility variance (s_R), the estimate of the between-laboratory variance (s_L), and their corresponding coefficients of variation ($C_{V,r}$, $C_{V,R}$ and $C_{V,L}$). For simplicity, in this work the term “standard deviations” will be used to refer to the “estimates”. It is worth noting that:

$$s_R^2 = s_r^2 + s_L^2 \quad (1)$$

The ratio $\frac{s_r}{s_R}$ was also calculated to assess the proportion of total variability attributable to repeatability. When this ratio is close to 1, interlaboratory variance is negligible, indicating that the method is well harmonized. Conversely, when the ratio is much less than 1, interlaboratory variance is significant, pointing to reproducibility issues. Statistical tests, such as Cochran's test (for detecting outliers in variances) and Grubbs' test (for detecting outliers in means), were applied to ensure the validity of interlaboratory data by identifying and removing anomalous results that could distort the estimation of precision, in agreement with the ISO 5725-2 guidelines. Finally, method recovery was calculated as the ratio between the overall mean of the results and the assigned value.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1. Evaluation of the performances of the ISO 16094-2 method on three different materials

Due to the limited number of reference material sets, and consequently of participants, it was decided to evaluate together the results obtained using Raman and μ (FT)IR for statistical analysis. For particles larger than 50 μm , the measurement capabilities of both techniques are comparable. Therefore, combining the results from Raman and μ (FT)IR in the data analysis was considered appropriate in order to increase the number of replicates.

Blank results were monitored for each dataset and will be addressed in the dedicated discussion section. In general, blank subtraction was not required. For all samples, results down to 50 μm were used for statistical evaluation, in line with the sample design. Additionally, for the ISO-C sample, the total number of microplastics down to 20 μm was also reported with special focus, in this case, on Raman results.

The method performance parameters evaluated according to ISO 5725-2 are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2. Performances of the ISO method evaluated on three different materials. l : number of participating laboratory; n : number of individual test results after outlier rejection; o : percentage of outliers; X : assigned value; \bar{x} : overall mean of results (without outliers); η : recovery; s_R : reproducibility standard deviation; $C_{V,R}$: coefficient of variation of reproducibility; s_r : repeatability standard deviation; $C_{V,r}$: coefficient of variation of repeatability; s_L : inter-laboratory standard deviation; $C_{V,inter}$: coefficient of inter-laboratory variation.

Tested materials	l	n	o	X	\bar{x}	η	s_R	$C_{V,R}$	s_r	$C_{V,r}$	s_L	$C_{V,L}$	s_r/s_R	Excluded labs
ISO-A MixA + MixB	11	32	5.9%	196	176	89.9%	95	54%	53	30%	79	45%	0.6	Lab. 10
ISO-A MixA or MixB	11	66	2.9%	98	88	89.9%	51	58%	31	36%	40	46%	0.6	Lab. 10
ISO-B	11	30	11.8%		262		162	62%	52	20%	154	59%	0.3	Lab. 3
ISO-C (size > 50 μm)	10	32	0.0%	28	15	53.2%	10	64%	7	45%	7	45%	0.7	-
ISO-C (size > 20 μm)	11	33	0.0%	78	46	59.1%	34	73%	22	48%	25	55%	0.7	-
ISO-C (size > 50 μm) - ONLY RAMAN	8	16	0.0%	28	18	62.5%	9	49%	5	26%	7	42%	0.5	-
ISO-C (size > 20 μm) - ONLY RAMAN	8	17	0.0%	98	60	61.6%	33	55%	12	21%	31	51%	0.4	-

5.2.ISO-A test material: measuring low concentration of microplastics with multiple polymer types

The evaluation of the ISO-A results was carried out using two approaches. In the first, Mix A and Mix B were treated as a single sample, with the total number of microplastics calculated as the sum of all six studied polymers (Fig. 1 and Table 2). In the second approach, Mix A and Mix B, that contain each the same total number of MPs, were considered as replicates (Fig. 2 and Table 2). In this case, the total number of microplastics was determined by summing the polymers in each tablet: (PE + PS + PVC) for Mix A and (PET + PP + PC) for Mix B. This approach has the advantage of increasing the number of replicates, thereby enabling a more robust statistical data treatment.

Fig. 1. Particle number measured in ISO-A test material by Raman and (FT)IR (individual measurements). Each point represents the sum of total spiked particles found in MixA and MixB combined. Red crosses indicate outlier measurements.

Fig. 2. Particle number measured in ISO-A test material by Raman and (FT)IR (individual measurements). Each point represents the sum of total spiked particles found in MixA or in MixB considered as replicates. Red crosses indicate outlier measurements.

One laboratory was excluded from the evaluation due to inconsistent results (Fig. 2). Overall, a high recovery rate was achieved across the remaining participants. The use of a harmonized method resulted in a reproducibility of approximately 50% (Table 2).

5.3. ISO-B test material: measuring higher concentration of microplastics with a single polymer type

Fig. 3. Particle number measured in ISO-B test material by Raman and (FT)IR (individual measurements). Each point represents the total number of PET particles. Red crosses indicate outlier measurements.

Low values reported by Lab03 correspond to (FT)IR measurements (Fig. 3). Since no assigned value is available, and considering homogeneity as well as short- and long-term stability, a particle count in the range of 302–484 (Ferret min) is expected. One laboratory was excluded from the evaluation. The observed repeatability of 20% is an improvement compared to the ISO-A material. However, the low sr/sR ratio of 0.3 (Table 2) highlights considerable interlaboratory variability, indicating reproducibility issues.

5.4. ISO-C test material: through low microplastic concentration in smaller size classes

All laboratories were included in the evaluation. The material showed a high repeatability of 45% compared to the ISO-A material, with a slight increase when measuring the 20 µm size class (Table 4). Interlaboratory variance was comparable to that observed for the ISO-A material, rising to 55% for the 20 µm size class.

Fig. 4. Particle number measured in ISO-C test material by Raman and (FT)IR (individual measurements). Each point represents the total number of PET particles measured which size is: A) higher than 50 μm; B) higher than 20 μm.

6. CONCLUSION

This interlaboratory comparison has provided the first comprehensive validation of ISO 16094-2 for the detection, identification, and quantification of microplastics in water using μ (FT)IR and μ Raman spectroscopy. Across three reference materials of varying polymer types, particle concentrations, and size classes, the method demonstrated satisfactory performance in terms of recovery and repeatability, particularly for particles $\geq 50 \mu\text{m}$. However, reproducibility remained limited, with significant interlaboratory variability evident, especially for complex mixtures (ISO-A) and in the case of ISO-B, despite improved repeatability. The evaluation of ISO-C confirmed that measurements can be extended down to $20 \mu\text{m}$, but variability increased at smaller size classes, underscoring the analytical challenges at the lower detection limit. Overall, the results confirm the robustness of the ISO 16094-2 methodology under repeatability conditions, while highlighting reproducibility as the main source of uncertainty. These findings reinforce the need for further harmonisation of analytical practices, improved training, and the development of well-characterised reference materials below $50 \mu\text{m}$. Such advances will be critical to ensuring comparability of results across laboratories and to supporting reliable monitoring of microplastics in environmental and drinking water.

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